

CONCEPT OF AGNI IN MAINTAINING CARDIOVASCULAR HEALTH

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ABSTRACT

The incidences of cardiovascular event are increasing, and even younger populations and children are now at risk. There is a growing need for people to become aware and take preventive measures before experiencing these conditions. In Ayurveda, Nidan Parivarjan (avoiding causative factors) is a fundamental principle for disease prevention. Ayurvedic texts highlight Agni as the primary determinant of maintaining Swasthya (health). When Agni is disturbed, it leads to the formation of Ama, considered the root cause of many diseases. Therefore, timely assessment and maintenance of Agni are important for preventing pathological conditions. This study examines the relationship between Agni, as described in Ayurveda, and cardiovascular diseases (Hrudroga), and reviews modern research linking gut microbiota disturbances to cardiovascular diseases. The central argument is that understanding and maintaining Agni in balance may help prevent cardiovascular

diseases.

KEYWORDS: Cardiovascular diseases, Agni, Gut microbiota, Hrudroga, Ama, Prevention.

INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular Diseases (CVD) pose a significant health challenge due to their prevalence and potential for causing long-term disability and premature death. However, with proper awareness and lifestyle modification, many of these disorders can be effectively managed.

Cardiovascular diseases are very common now a day. These diseases affect the heart and blood vessels. According to WHO, they are responsible for an estimated 17.9 million deaths each year, and are the leading cause of death globally.

In Ayurveda, Hridaya (heart) has been mentioned as a physical and emotional health centre. In Ayurvedic text, the word of Hrudroga, Hrudshula and Hrudayama has been used for Cardiovascular Diseases. Five types of Hrudrogas have been mentioned by Acharyas. The causes of Hrudrogas have been described in the ancient text. As the Ayurveda science focuses on prevention, which can be achieved by lifestyle modification. Mental stress, disturbed daily routine and faulty dietary practices are the route cause of Cardiovascular diseases. Here we can educate people about the way of comprehensive lifestyle modification to restore the harmony of the systems in the body. There are many diet related concepts mentioned in Ayurvedic Samhitas. In Ayurveda Triupastambhas has mentioned which includes Aahar-Nidra and Bramhachariya. Aahara is mentioned as the first pillar among the Triupastambhas. The importance of Aahara(food) is mentioned in many contexts. Food supports the Dhatus (body tissue), Oja (immunity), Bala (strength) and Varna (complexion). Aahara according to Ayurveda must be Rutasatmaya (Adjusted according to weather), Pathyakara, Shadrasatmak, Aviruddha, Matravata (must be according to Agnibala). Agni is a variable factor. The assessment of Agni from time to time is definitely essential for determining and adjusting the quantity of diet.

CAUSES OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES (CVD)

Causes of Cardiovascular Diseases (CVD) include Hypertension (High BP), metabolic disorders like dyslipidaemia, Diabetes, Obesity, lifestyle changes like eating unhealthy food, physical inactivity, stressful work schedules and addiction like smoking and excessive alcohol consumption.

According to Ayurveda causes of Hrudrogas as described in Madhavidan are, Atiushna (eating food having warm potency), Guru (food which are heavy to digest), Kashaya-Tikt sevan (Astringents and bitter in taste), Shrama (stannous exercise for long duration), Abhighata (injury), Adhyashan (eating food before the previous eaten food has not digested), Chinta (Worry), Vegavidharan (suppression of natural urges).

According to Ayurveda prevention perspective of CVD can be possible by correcting the risk factors through many measures. Healthy eating habits are one among them. In Ayurveda, the

Ahara (food) that we consume gets digested, absorbed, assimilated and transformed into body tissue by the Agni (digestive fire) and the Tridosha (Vata-Pitta-Kapha). Here in the article we are going to focus on the concept of Agni mentioned in Ayurvedic context, its type and importance in prevention of Cardiovascular Diseases (CVD).

METABOLISM OF FOOD ACCORDING TO AYURVEDA

1. Jatharagni

According to Ayurveda, the process of digestion starts in Annavaha Srotas, which is primarily governed by Jatharagni. This process involves 3 stages: - Madhura Avastha Paka: Occurs in the stomach, where physical breakdown of food particles is done. Kapha Dosha is dominant in this phase. - Amla Avastha Paka: Takes place in the small intestine, where the dominant Dosha is Pitta. The transformation of food continues here. - Katu Avastha Paka: Occurs in the large intestine, where absorption and separation of waste take place under the influence of Vata Dosha.

2. Bhutagni

After the initial action of Jatharagni, the food is broken down into subtle levels by the action of Bhutagni (fire associated with the five Mahabhutas). Each Mahabhutagni metabolizes its portion to prepare it for tissue formation.

3. Dhatvagni

After the action of Bhutagni, the food finally gets transformed into the seven Dhatus by the action of Dhatvagni.

PHYSIOLOGICAL CATEGORIES OF AGNI

Four type of Agni is determined by the action of Doshas.

Mandagni: In Kapha Dosha dominance, this Agni is unable to metabolize a moderate amount of food.

Tikshanagni: In Pitta Dosha dominance, the Agni digest heavy food in a shorter time duration and the urge of hunger frequently.

Vishamagni: By the influence of Vata Dosha the action of Agni becomes irregular. Sometimes it digests food faster as an urge of hugely quickly while some times it shows loss of appetite.

Samagni: When Tridoshas are in equilibrium, the food we eat will get digested without any irregularities.

AGNI AS A CAUSE OF DISEASE

Each Agni plays an important role in overall metabolism. If Agni is in its balanced state, it will nourish the whole body tissues properly. If the Agni is damaged, it will form Ama (undigested food/toxins), which is the root cause of disease. In Rasavaha Srotas, Ahara Rasa gets converted into Rasa Dhatu, and the Hridaya (heart) and Dashamni (10 main vessels) are the Moolasthanas of Rasavaha Srotas. If the quality or quantity of food and Agni mismatches, it leads to disturbance in Pachana (digestion), resulting in the formation of unusual Rasa Dhatu, which impacts Hridaya and Dashamni—the Moola of Rasavaha Srotas. In determination of Matra of Aahara depends on the status of Agni of that individual.

According to Ayurveda all the diseases are originated from Mandagni (Low digestive capacity), including Udararoga, Arsha, Atisara, Grahani and many more. Due to the vitiation of Agni, the development of Ama (Toxin) took place, which creates Strotorodha (channel blockage), which is the cause behind any disease. In modern science, many researches highlight the importance of good digestion and good cardiovascular health. In research, it has mentioned that cardiovascular diseases and digestive discomfort are the two sides of the same coin. According to the study, gut dysbiosis, which can be induced by obesity, aging, lifestyle or medication, both promotes gut inflammation and reduces gut barrier integrity. In turn, this increases the circulation of different types of metabolites that facilitate the pathophysiology of cardiovascular diseases.¹ According to modern science, imbalanced gut microbiota leads to cardiovascular disease as it produces inflammation, producing TMAO (Trimethylamine-N-oxide), which is linked with high risk of atherosclerosis (plaque formation in arteries) and it also interferes with fat metabolism resulting in other cardiovascular diseases. Dysbiosis can produce harmful substances that enters the blood stream and affect the heart.

CONCLUSION

In the present article, we can conclude that Agni plays a very important role at the cellular level. Assessment of Agni is essential to prevent Hrudroga. If Agni is in a normal state, it will metabolize food particles systematically. Thus, metabolic waste will not accumulate in the body. When Agni functions properly, each Dhatu (tissue) receives proper nutrition and eliminates its Mala (metabolic waste) efficiently. As a result, metabolic waste does not accumulate in the body, which helps prevent cardiovascular diseases. In modern science, the

health of gut microbiota is discussed in relation to cardiovascular diseases. In Ayurveda, understanding the concept of Agni could help prevent cardiovascular diseases.

REFERENCES

1. <https://www.who.int/health-topics/hypertension/cardiovascular-diseases>
2. <https://nutraceuticalbusinessreview.com/cardiovascular-disease-and-digestive-discomfort-two-sides-of-the-same-coin-210271>
3. Madhav nidana, Madhukosha teeka, Hrudroga nidanam 29/01
4. Tang WHW, Li DY, Hazen SL. Dietary metabolism, the gut microbiome, and heart failure. *Nat Rev Cardiol*, Mar. 2019; 16(3): 137-154. doi: 10.1038/s41569-018-0108-7. PMID: 30410105; PMCID: PMC6377322.
5. M. Novakovic, *et al.*, Role of Gut Microbiota in Cardiovascular Diseases, *World J. Cardiol*, 2020; 12(4): 110-122.
6. Trikamji Yadavji, Commentary Ayurve dadipika of Cakrapanidatta on Caraka samhita of Agnivesa, Chikitsa Sthana; grahani chikitsa: Chapter 15, Verse 15, Varanasi: Chowkhambha Surbharati Prakashan, 2017; 514-517.